

Adherence to Antiretroviral Therapy (ART) and Associated Factors Among Adult HIV Patients at the Benue State University Teaching Hospital, Makurdi, Nigeria

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Article information

Date Submitted: 28/03/2026

Date Accepted: 29/04/2026

Date Published: 03/06/2026

ABSTRACT

Background: Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) infection remains a major global public health problem despite significant progress in prevention, diagnosis, and treatment. In 2024, approximately 31.6 million people living with HIV (PLHIV) were receiving antiretroviral therapy (ART) globally, while about 76% of PLHIV in West and Central Africa were on ART. However, ART coverage reflects treatment access rather than treatment success. Optimal outcomes depend on ART adherence, traditionally defined as taking $\geq 95\%$ of prescribed doses. This study assessed the level of ART adherence among adult HIV patients at Benue State University Teaching Hospital, Makurdi, Nigeria, and identified the facilitators, barriers, and determinants of adherence.

Methodology: A cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted among HIV-positive adults attending the ART clinic. Respondents were selected using systematic random sampling. Data were collected between November and December 2025 using pre-tested, interviewer-administered questionnaires. Adherence was measured by patient self-report as the proportion of prescribed doses taken over the preceding three days. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 27. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, and means \pm SD) were used to summarize data. Crude odds ratios (COR) and adjusted odds ratios (AOR) were calculated to identify factors associated with adherence. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: Of the 298 respondents, 91 (30.5%) were males and 207 (69.5%) females, with a mean age of 38.94 ± 12.64 years. Overall, 86.6% reported good adherence, while 13.4% were non-adherent. Reported facilitators included confidence in taking ART as prescribed (95.3%), keeping medications in visible locations (94.6%), social support (62.4%), and use of reminders (55.4%). Reported barriers included fear of disclosure or stigma (15.1%), being away from home (8.4%), running out of ARVs (7.0%), and being busy (5.7%). Confidence in taking ART as prescribed was a significant predictor of adherence (AOR = 7.60, 95% CI: 1.11–51.81, $p = 0.038$). Being away from home (AOR = 0.005, 95% CI: 0.001–0.032, $p < 0.001$) and running out of ARVs (AOR = 0.003, 95% CI: 0.000–0.038, $p < 0.001$) were associated with significantly lower odds of adherence. Other variables were not significant after adjustment.

Conclusion: ART adherence was high among respondents. The main facilitator predicting adherence was confidence in taking ART as prescribed, while key barriers predicting lower odds of adherence were being away from home and

How to cite this article

*Shaahu VN, Bitto TT, Rimamnunra GN, Agbo E, Aondosoo AE, De-Kaa NLP. Adherence to Antiretroviral Therapy (ART) and Associated Factors Among Adult HIV Patients at the Benue State University Teaching Hospital, Makurdi, Nigeria. *J Biomed Res Clin Pract*: 2026;9(2):58-69. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20529223>

Access to the article

Website: <http://www.jbrcp.org>

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20529223

running out of medication. Interventions aimed at enhancing self-efficacy, strengthening social support systems, promoting the use of reminders, and encouraging advance planning for medication refills - especially during travel - may further improve adherence.

Keywords: Adherence, antiretroviral therapy (ART), adult HIV patients, Makurdi, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) infection continues to remain a global public health problem, despite significant progress in its prevention, diagnosis and treatment. Globally, according to the Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS (UNAIDS), there were about 40.8 million people living with HIV (PLHIV) by the end of 2024,¹ with Western and Central Africa accounting for about 5.2 million PLHIV.^{1,2} In 2018, the Nigeria HIV/AIDS Indicator and Impact Survey (NAIIS) reported a national HIV prevalence of 1.4% in adults aged 15-64 years, compared with 4.8% in Benue State – a prevalence that is more than three times the national average.³ Furthermore, as of 2019, an estimated 1.8 million people were living with HIV in Nigeria.⁴

While millions of people are living with HIV worldwide, access to antiretroviral therapy (ART) determines who can benefit from treatment. Globally, about 31.6 million PLHIV were receiving ART in 2024, representing about 77% of all PLHIV.¹ In West and Central Africa, about 76% of PLHIV were on ART in 2024.^{1,2} In Nigeria, over 1.1 million PLHIV were on ART in 2019, giving a treatment coverage of 63.6%.⁴

Nevertheless, ART coverage reflects treatment reach rather than treatment success. Understanding the benefits of ART helps to contextualize why treatment success - not just access - is essential. ART has transformed HIV infection from a fatal disease into a manageable chronic condition.^{5,6} By suppressing viral replication to undetectable levels,^{5,7} ART preserves or restores immune function,^{6,7} prolongs survival and reduces HIV-related morbidity⁶ and mortality,^{8,9} prevents onward transmission to others,^{6,7} and improves quality of life among people living with HIV.¹⁰ However, for the successful treatment of HIV infection, adherence to ART is crucial.¹¹ The clinical and public health benefits of ART are achieved when patients

maintain optimal adherence, traditionally defined as taking $\geq 95\%$ of prescribed doses.¹¹ Nonetheless, emerging evidence suggests that the level of adherence required to achieve viral suppression may be lower than previously thought and can vary depending on the type of regimen being used.¹²

Despite its importance, adherence to ART remains a major challenge among people living with HIV globally. Earlier systematic reviews reported comparatively higher adherence levels in Africa and Asia than in Europe and North America.^{13,14} In high-income settings, adherence rates ranged from approximately 50-60% in studies published in 2006¹³ and 2014¹⁴. In contrast, adherence in low- and middle-income settings exceeded 70%,¹⁴ with pooled estimates in sub-Saharan Africa reaching 77%.¹³

More recent evidence indicates that ART adherence in sub-Saharan Africa varies widely. A 2024 systematic review reported adherence levels ranging from 43% to 84%.¹⁵ Individual country studies have documented relatively high adherence rates, including 83.3% in Ethiopia (2021)¹⁶ and 83.1% in Zambia and 85.5% in South Africa (2020).¹⁷ In contrast, lower adherence levels have been reported in Nigeria, with estimates of 54% and 60.1% in 2024.¹⁵ However, within Benue State, Nigeria, a study conducted in Makurdi in 2023 reported adherence rates of 77.5% over the preceding 7 days and 78.8% over the preceding 3 months among adults living with HIV.¹⁸ These variations across settings highlight persistent gaps in achieving optimal treatment outcomes.

Suboptimal adherence undermines the benefits of antiretroviral therapy (ART), contributes to drug resistance and treatment failure, and hinders progress toward achieving viral suppression targets.^{19,20} Understanding adherence patterns and their determinants is therefore critical to strengthening the HIV care continuum and advancing global and national

treatment goals. Furthermore, in the context of evolving ART delivery models and treatment regimens, there is a need for updated evidence to better understand the factors influencing adherence and to inform targeted, context-specific interventions in high-burden settings such as Benue State, Nigeria. Against this backdrop, this study therefore aimed to assess the level of adherence to ART among adult HIV patients at Benue State University Teaching Hospital, Makurdi, Nigeria, and to identify the facilitators, barriers, and determinants of adherence.

METHODOLOGY

Study Area and Setting

The study was conducted in Makurdi, the capital of Benue State, located in the North-Central geopolitical zone of Nigeria. Benue State had a projected population of approximately 6.1 million in 2022²¹ and is predominantly agrarian. Makurdi serves as the administrative and commercial centre of the state and hosts several healthcare facilities that provide specialized services, including HIV care.

The study was carried out at the antiretroviral therapy (ART) clinic of Benue State University Teaching Hospital (BSUTH), Makurdi. Established in 2016, the clinic provides comprehensive HIV care and currently serves approximately 1,000 people living with HIV (PLHIV). The clinic is a key centre for HIV programme monitoring, patient follow-up, and community outreach activities in the State.

In addition to ART services, the clinic offers tuberculosis screening and Directly Observed Treatment, Short-course (DOTS); cervical cancer screening for female clients; and specialized support for survivors of gender-based violence (GBV). This integration of services is in line with the Nigeria national HIV prevention, treatment and care guidelines.²² ART, cervical cancer screening and GBV services are offered on Tuesdays and Fridays; while tuberculosis screening and DOTS are offered Mondays through Fridays.

Study Design and Population

A cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted

among HIV-positive adults (≥ 18 years) attending the ART clinic. Eligible participants were those aged 18 years or older, on ART for at least three months, clinically stable, and who provided informed consent. Adults who had been on ART for less than three months, were acutely ill, or declined participation were excluded from the study. Patients on ART for less than three months were excluded because early adherence is often unstable and influenced by treatment initiation factors, and may not reflect sustained adherence patterns.

Sample Size Calculation and Sampling Technique

The minimum sample size was calculated using the formula for descriptive cross-sectional studies: $n = z^2pq/d^2$. Where n is the minimum sample size, z is the standard normal deviate at 95% confidence interval (1.96), p is the proportion of HIV-positive adults adherent to ART in a previous study in Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria (77.5%),¹⁸ q is complementary probability (1- p), and d is the margin of error set at 0.05. After compensating for a 10% non-response rate, the calculated sample size was 298.

A systematic random sampling technique was used to select participants for the study. The ART clinic at BSUTH runs on Tuesdays and Fridays, with an average of about 50 adult patients attending weekly. This translated to an estimated 400 adult patients over a two-month period. The sampling interval (k) was calculated by dividing the estimated population by the required sample size ($k = N/n = 400/298 = 1.34$), which was approximated to 1. Therefore, all eligible patients were consecutively recruited until the desired sample size was achieved.

Research Instrument and Data Collection

The questionnaire was developed based on a review of relevant literature and aligned with the study objectives. Content validity was assessed by experts in public health and HIV research. The instrument comprised sections on socio-demographic and clinical characteristics, a 3-day self-reported adherence measure, and perceived facilitators and barriers to adherence. Data were collected between November and December 2025 by the investigator and two research assistants who were final-

year medical students. The research assistants received standardized instruction on the study protocol, including questionnaire administration procedures and the calculation of the 3-day self-reported adherence measure. The questionnaire was interviewer-administered and pre-tested prior to the main data collection to ensure clarity, appropriateness, and ease of administration. Necessary modifications were made following the pre-test.

Variables of the Study

The outcome (dependent) variable was adherence to antiretroviral therapy (ART). Adherence was measured using patient self-report and calculated as the proportion of prescribed antiretroviral doses taken over the preceding three days. For the purpose of this study, adherence was categorized as “adherent” for patients who reported taking 100% of their prescribed doses during the 3-day period, and “non-adherent” for those who reported taking less than 100% of their prescribed doses. The explanatory (independent) variables included socio-demographic and clinical characteristics, facilitators of adherence, and barriers to adherence.

Data Analyses

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 27. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, and means (\pm SD), were used to summarize the data. Crude odds ratios (COR) were computed to assess bivariate associations between independent variables and ART adherence. Variables with $p < 0.20$ in the bivariate analysis, as well as those considered theoretically important (including age), were entered into a multivariable logistic regression model to estimate adjusted odds ratios (AOR) and identify independent predictors of adherence. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval (BSUTH/MKD/HREC/2026/282) was obtained from the Ethical Review Committee of the Benue State University Teaching Hospital, Makurdi. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants before data collection. Interviews were

conducted privately within the ART clinic to ensure confidentiality, and participants' anonymity was maintained. All data were securely stored and accessible only to the research team.

RESULTS

Socio-demographic and clinical characteristics

Table 1 presents socio-demographic and clinical characteristics. A total of 298 respondents participated in the study, with the majority being female (69.5%). The mean age was 38.94 ± 12.64 years, and most were aged 30-39 years (34.0%). Over half were married (54.7%), and the majority had at least secondary education (72.8%). Slightly more than half were employed (53.7%), and most lived with their nuclear family (71.1%). Regarding clinical characteristics, most respondents had been diagnosed with HIV for three years or more (66.8%), and a large proportion (82.6%) had been on ART for less than one year. About half (51.3%) had an undetectable viral load.

Facilitators and barriers to ART adherence

Table 2 presents facilitators and barriers to ART adherence. The main facilitators of ART adherence were confidence in taking ARVs as prescribed (95.3%), keeping ARVs where they could be remembered (94.6%), and the provision of free ARVs (98.0%). Over half of the respondents also reported social support (62.4%) and use of reminders (55.4%), while only a few attended support group meetings (9.1%). On the other hand, 15.1% of the respondents avoided taking their ARVs due to fear of disclosure or stigma. Other barriers included being away from home (8.4%), forgetting to take doses (8.1%), running out of ARVs (7.0%) and being busy (5.7%).

Table 1: Sociodemographic and clinical characteristics

	Frequency	Percentage
Socio-demographic characteristics		
Sex		
Male	91	30.5
Female	207	69.5
Age (years)		
<20	18	6
20 – 29	46	15.4
30 – 39	101	34.0
40 – 49	82	27.5
≥ 50	51	17.1
Mean ± SD = 38.94 ± 12.64		
Marital status		
Single	93	31.2
Married	163	54.7
Separated	6	2.0
Divorced	7	2.3
Widowed	29	9.7
Educational level		
No formal education	41	13.8
Primary education	40	13.4
Secondary education	143	48.0
Tertiary education	74	24.8
Employment Status		
Employed	160	53.7
Unemployed	138	46.3
Living Situation		
Living alone	61	20.5
Living with nuclear family	212	71.1
Living with extended family	25	8.4
Clinical characteristics		
Duration since HIV diagnosis		
<3 years	99	33.2
≥3 years	199	66.8
Duration on ART		
< 1 year	246	82.6
≥ 1 year	52	17.4
Viral load		
Undetectable	153	51.3
Detectable	145	48.7

Figure 1: Level of ART adherence

Level of ART adherence

Figure 1 presents the level of adherence. Majority of the respondents were adherent to ART, 258 (86.6%), while 40 (13.4%) were non-adherent.

Crude and adjusted odds ratios of determinants of ART adherence

Table 3 presents the results of bivariate analysis (crude odds ratios, COR) and multivariable logistic regression analysis (adjusted odds ratios, AOR) for factors associated with ART adherence. Of the socio-demographic and clinical characteristics assessed, none met the predefined threshold ($p < 0.20$) at bivariate analysis for inclusion in the multivariable logistic regression model. However, age was included in the adjusted analysis due to its established theoretical and empirical relevance to adherence.

In the bivariate analysis, social support, confidence in taking ART as prescribed, and keeping ARVs in locations where they could be easily remembered were significantly associated with adherence ($p < 0.05$). In contrast, being away from home and running out of ARVs were significantly associated with lower adherence ($p < 0.05$).

In the multivariable logistic regression analysis, confidence in taking ART as prescribed remained a significant predictor of adherence (AOR = 7.60, 95% CI: 1.11–51.81, $p = 0.038$). Conversely, being away from home (AOR = 0.005, 95% CI: 0.001–0.032, $p < 0.001$) and running out of ARVs (AOR = 0.003, 95% CI: 0.000–0.038, $p < 0.001$) were significantly associated with lower odds of adherence. Other factors, including age, use of reminders, social support, and keeping ARVs in memorable locations, were not statistically significant after adjustment.

Table 2: Facilitators and barriers to ART adherence

	Frequency	Percentage
Facilitators		
Use reminders		
Yes	165	55.4
No	133	44.6
Attend ART clinic support group meetings		
Yes	27	9.1
No	271	90.9
Enjoy social support		
Yes	186	62.4
No	112	37.6
Confident about taking ARVs as prescribed		
Yes	284	95.3
No	14	4.7
Keep ARVs where it can be remembered		
Yes	282	94.6
No	16	5.4
Provision of free ARVs reduces concerns about access		
Yes	292	98
No	6	2.0
Barriers		
Forgot to take ARVs		
Yes	24	8.1
No	274	91.9
Avoided taking ARVs due to fear of disclosure/stigma		
Yes	45	15.1
No	253	84.9
Away from home		
Yes	25	8.4
No	273	91.6
Ran out of ARVs		
Yes	21	7.0
No	277	93.0
Busy		
Yes	17	5.7
No	281	94.3

Table 3: Crude and adjusted odds ratios of determinants of ART adherence

Factors	COR (95% CI)	P-value	AOR (95% CI)	P-value
Age (years)				
<40 years	0.71 (0.36-1.41)	0.331	2.42 (0.64-9.09)	0.191
≥40 years	Reference		Reference	
Use of reminders				
Yes	1.62 (0.83-3.16)	0.159	0.27 (0.06-1.17)	0.080
No	Reference		Reference	
Enjoy social support				
Yes	3.28 (1.64-6.53)	0.001	1.33 (0.39-4.51)	0.647
No	Reference		Reference	
Confident about taking ART				
Yes	10.50 (3.42-32.20)	<0.001	7.60 (1.11-51.81)	0.038*
No	Reference		Reference	
Keep ARVs where it can be remembered				
Yes	7.81 (2.74-22.25)	<0.001	5.51 (0.89-34.11)	0.067
No	Reference		Reference	
Away from home				
Yes	0.006 (0.001-0.027)	<0.001	0.005 (0.001-0.032)	<0.001*
No	Reference		Reference	
Ran out of ARVs				
Yes	0.004 (0.000-0.031)	<0.001	0.003 (0.000-0.038)	<0.001*
No	Reference		Reference	

Note: Hosmer-Lemeshow goodness of fit test: $\chi^2 = 3.65$, $df = 8$, $p = 0.887$
 COR = crude odds ratio; AOR = adjusted odds ratio; CI = confidence interval
 *Statistically significant

DISCUSSION

Adherence rate

Overall, adherence was high, with 86.6% of respondents reporting good adherence, while 13.4% were non-adherent. This finding has important implications for clinical and public health practice, as high adherence is essential for achieving viral suppression, reducing the risk of drug resistance, improving patient clinical outcomes, and prevents onward transmission to others.^{6,7} The high adherence rate in the present study is consistent with other studies in sub-Saharan Africa, which have reported adherence levels ranging from 83% to 85.5%.^{16,17} However, lower adherence rates of 77.5% in the preceding 7 days and 78.8% in the preceding 3 months, were reported among adults living with HIV in an earlier study conducted in Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria.¹⁸ These differences in adherence rates may be partly explained by variations in patient-level factors (including sociodemographic characteristics, knowledge and belief about ART, social support, HIV-related stigma and fear of disclosure, substance use, depression and anxiety), study populations, settings, and methods of measuring adherence, including differences in recall periods.

Socio-demographic and clinical characteristics

In this study, none of the socio-demographic and clinical characteristics assessed met the threshold for inclusion in the multivariable logistic regression model. Age, which was included in the model due to its theoretical and empirical relevance, was also not significantly associated with adherence. This pattern suggests that socio-demographic and clinical characteristics may have a limited influence on adherence within this study population. In contrast to the present study, previous studies have identified socio-demographic and clinical characteristics - such as age, sex, education, baseline CD4 count, and comorbidities - as significant predictors of ART adherence in various settings.^{16,23-25}

Facilitators and barriers to ART adherence

The main facilitator predicting adherence was confidence in taking ARVs as prescribed. This finding is

consistent with previous studies showing that self-efficacy - that is, believing in one's ability to consistently manage treatment - is positively associated with ART adherence.^{23,26-28} Moreover, higher levels of self-efficacy have been linked to greater medication adherence.²⁶ This suggests that supporting patients to build confidence through counselling, education, and practical strategies may significantly improve adherence.

Other facilitators identified in the crude analysis, but not retained after adjustment, included social support and keeping ARVs in easily remembered locations. Although these factors did not remain significant in the adjusted model, they are still important in understanding adherence behaviour. For example, a simple strategy such as keeping medication in a consistent, visible location may help reduce forgetfulness. In addition, social support has been widely reported as a key facilitator of ART adherence.²⁹⁻³² Supportive relationships can provide reminders, encouragement, emotional support, and practical assistance, all of which may promote consistent medication use.

Being away from home and running out of ARVs were significant barriers identified in the study. Although ART services - including free ARVs, multi-month dispensing, and early refill options - are available at the study site, some respondents still reported running out of ARVs. This suggests that factors beyond service availability may be contributing to this challenge. For example, transport costs, competing financial demands, or time constraints may limit patients' ability to attend clinic appointments. While these factors were not directly assessed in the present study, they have been identified as important barriers to ART adherence in similar settings.^{30,31,33}

Strengths and limitations

This study has several strengths. It used direct data collection from ART clinic patients, allowing for a detailed assessment of socio-demographic, clinical, and behavioural factors influencing adherence. By examining both facilitators and barriers, and applying crude and adjusted logistic regression analyses, the study was able to identify significant independent

predictors of adherence while accounting for potential confounders. Importantly, some of the identified factors - such as confidence in taking medication (self-efficacy) and medication management practices - are modifiable, making these findings relevant for designing practical, actionable interventions.

Some limitations should also be considered. The cross-sectional design limits the ability to establish causality. In addition, adherence was self-reported and may be subject to recall or social desirability bias. Furthermore, some potentially important factors - such as mental health, transport-related challenges, and other health system barriers - were not directly assessed. This is particularly relevant given that some respondents reported running out of ARVs despite the availability of services, suggesting that unmeasured contextual factors may influence adherence. Despite these limitations, the study provides useful insights into the key drivers of ART adherence and highlights important areas for intervention in similar settings.

CONCLUSION

In this study, adherence was high, with 86.6% of respondents reporting good adherence, while 13.4% were non-adherent. Several important factors influencing adherence to antiretroviral therapy among adult HIV-patients were identified. Confidence in taking ART as prescribed emerged as the strongest predictor of adherence, highlighting the important role of self-efficacy in supporting consistent medication use. Although social support and practical strategies such as keeping ARVs in easily remembered locations were associated with adherence at the crude level, these effects were not sustained after adjustment. However, they highlight the need for strengthening social support systems and improving medication management. In contrast, being away from home and running out of ARVs were significant barriers, suggesting that disruptions in routine and challenges with timely medication refills remain important contributors to non-adherence, even where ART services are readily available. These highlight the need for improving refill planning and clinic attendance.

Implications for practice

Based on the study findings, several practical interventions could strengthen ART adherence in the study population and similar settings. Enhancing self-efficacy is critical, and this can be achieved by building patients' confidence through ongoing adherence counselling and positive reinforcement. Such measures empower patients to take ownership of their treatment routine and manage it effectively. Strengthening social support is equally important, and involving treatment supporters can provide both encouragement and practical assistance. Patients should also be encouraged to adopt simple reminder strategies, including the use of visual cues such as pillboxes or markings on calendars, as well as alarms or phone notifications to promote consistent medication intake.

To address barriers related to timely medication refills, patients may be guided to plan ahead, particularly during travel, and supported through appointment reminders delivered via calls or messages. Rapid refill or fast-track systems should be made available for those with urgent needs. In addition, there is a need to maximize the use of existing ART services. While options such as multi-month dispensing and early refills are already in place, greater emphasis should be placed on ensuring patients fully utilize these services, attend clinic appointments on time, and avoid delays that could result in running out of medication. Together, these interventions provide actionable and sustainable strategies for improving adherence, thereby supporting better treatment outcomes and long-term health benefits.

Acknowledgements

The authors sincerely appreciate the patients who participated in this study. We also thank the final-year medical students who assisted with data collection, as well as the staff of the ART clinic at BSUTH, Makurdi, for their support.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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